

SYNERGISTIC STRENGTHENING OF SISAL FIBER WITH ALKALI TREATMENT AND CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS MODIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) has been used to improve the mechanical properties of natural fibers reinforced composites, but the strengthening effect was often limited by their adhesion and the deposition content of CNCs onto fiber surface. In this work, electrophoretic deposition (EPD) was employed to modify fibers with CNCs. This study also treated sisal fibers with alkali before EPD of CNCs, and investigated their synergistic effects on mechanical properties and interfacial properties of the fibers. The CNCs were prepared by acid hydrolysis of microcrystalline cellulose (MCC). Alkali (sodium hydroxide) concentrations were 5 wt%, and 0.5 wt% CNC suspensions were used to modify raw and alkali-treated fibers by EPD. All groups of fibers were subjected to tensile tests and single fiber pull-out tests with epoxy matrix. Results show that comparing to raw fiber, CNCs modified group has similar tensile properties. With alkali treatment, the tensile strength and Young's modulus of the sisal fibers were increased by 31% and 38%; with the same concentration alkali treatment, and then followed CNCs modification, sisal fibers has 62% higher Young's modulus. It revealed that alkali treatment promoted the stiffening of sisal fiber with CNCs. With regard to interfacial properties of sisal/epoxy composites, the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) of alkali-treated group were increased by 35%; while that of CNCs modified groups showed no obvious change, but CNCs modification made the process of pull-out turn into a stable mode. Based on experiment results, Gao-Mai-Cotterel's model was adopted to calculate the interfacial parameters, which showed that the frictional coefficient of CNCs modified groups were twice more than that of untreated and alkali-treated groups. To further reveal and prove these interfacial mechanisms, fractured surface morphology of fibers was characterized by SEM and optical microscope.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fibers reinforced polymer composites have recently attracted the attention of scientists and engineers because of the advantages of low cost, low density, high specific strength and modulus [1]. Moreover, they are renewable and biodegradable, unlike other conventional reinforcing fibers. Sisal fiber is one of the most widely used natural fibers and highly adapted to different processes of composites preparation [2]. In addition to the mechanical properties of reinforcing fibers, properties of fiber-reinforced composites also depend on fiber-matrix adhesion as well as stress transfer efficiency of interface. The potential strength and toughness of natural fiber reinforced composites have not yet been exploited because of the poor interface between hydrophilic fiber and hydrophobic polymer matrices. Different surface modifications of natural fibers have been carried out for better compatibility with polymer matrix [3]. Alkali treatment is one of the most used chemical treatment of natural fibers [4, 5]. It removes some surface impurities such as wax, oils, and a certain amount of lignin and hemicelluloses, covering the external surface of the fiber cell wall [6]. Stiffer natural fibers [7] and improved interfacial adhesion [8] are obtained by alkali treatment.

With the development of nanotechnology and biotechnology, new approaches have also recently been employed to modify natural fibers. Cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) is pure highly crystalline cellulose, extracted from wood, plant, tunicate and bacteria. CNC is an ideal reinforcing material,

which has a greater axial elastic modulus (110-220 GPa) than Kevlar and its tensile strength (1.5-7.7 GPa) within the range of other reinforcement materials [9, 10]. Dasong Dai et al. [11] produced CNCs from hemp fibers and employed them to modify hemp fibers themselves with the assistance of surfactant. The results showed CNCs modification increased tensile strength and modulus of hemp fibers. Bismarck et al. [12, 13] used the bacterial cellulose to modify hemp fibers and sisal fibers. By using biological technology, hierarchical fiber reinforced nanocomposites were successfully created, and tensile properties of modified sisal fiber reinforced composites obtained significant improvements due to the enhancement of the interfacial performance.

Although it is available to use CNCs to improve the mechanical properties of natural fibers reinforced composites successfully, the strengthening effect is often limited by their adhesion and the deposition content of CNCs onto fiber surface. Based on our preliminary research work, both the surface morphology and mechanical properties of sisal fibers treated by directly soaking in the CNCs suspension had no obvious variation, although lots of hydroxyl groups on the surface of them could form hydrogen bonds, which promoted the adsorption of CNCs. EPD is a convenient, rapid and versatile coating technique that promotes the movement of charged particles in suspension to one of the electrodes under an appropriate electric field [14]. Due to the partial esterification reaction between the sulfate and hydroxyl groups during the acid hydrolysis production of CNCs, it leads to stable suspension of the negative charged CNCs, which is applicable to EPD process.

In this work, we used EPD as a new method for attaching CNCs to sisal fiber surface within a high concentration. Attempts are made to enhance the mechanical properties of sisal fibers and their interfacial performance with epoxy by both alkali treatment and CNCs modification. Inspired by the ability of alkali treatment to change fiber structure to create a large interfibrillar gap for CNCs coating, we investigated synergistic effects of both treating steps. Meanwhile, individual effects of either alkali treatment or CNCs coating are evaluated to exclude their own roles.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENT

2.1. Materials

Sisal fibers were obtained from Guangxi Province, China. Commercial MCC powder (particle size, 20~80 μm), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH, AR) and Sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4 , 98 wt%) were purchased from Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co., Ltd, Shanghai, China. Epoxy resin (NPEL-128), curing agent (EH-6303) and accelerator (EH-6412) (100:26:8) were provided by Nanya Electronic Materials (Kunshan) Co., Ltd.

2.2. Preparation of CNCs

CNCs were prepared by sulphuric acid hydrolysis of MCC following the recipe reported by Cranston and Gray. 20 grams of MCC were added into 200 mL of H_2SO_4 (65 wt%) solution. The hydrolysis process was performed at 50 $^\circ\text{C}$ under stirring (600 r/min) for 2h. Then the suspension was washed with deionized water using repeated centrifuge cycles (10 min at 10,000 rpm) until the supernatant became turbid. The colloidal suspension was then dialysed in the deionized water for a week to remove the residual acid. Finally, the CNCs sample were sonicated in an ice bath for 10 min to a stable suspension, in which the concentration of CNCs was 12 mg/mL determined by measure the mass of freeze-dried CNCs. The yield of CNCs was then calculated, which was about 35.9%.

2.3 Modification of sisal fibers

The sisal fibers were first washed with deionized water at 70 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1h to remove some impurities and dirt, then followed by a drying process in a vacuum oven at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$. The washed sisal fibers were designated as untreated fibers and were subjected to alkali and CNCs modification.

a) Alkali treatment: The sisal fibers were treated in 5 wt% NaOH solution for 2 h at 23 $^\circ\text{C}$, then washed thoroughly with deionized water and finally vacuum dried to get alkali-treated fibers.

b) CNCs modification by EPD: Both the untreated and alkali-treated sisal fibers were modified by CNCs with EPD method. Figure 1 schematically shows the deposition procedure of CNCs on the sisal fiber surface. Steel plates were placed on both sides as counter electrode at a gap of 1 cm. Because

CNCs were negative charged in the suspension, the fibers were fixed to the anode plate. 400 mL CNCs suspension (5 mg/mL) was used to carry out EPD. DC voltage of 20V was applied to the suspension for 5 min. Thereafter the fibers were taken out and dried. The final obtained fibers were named CNCs modified and Alkali-CNCs modified fibers, respectively.

Figure 1: Schematic of electrophoretic deposition setup.

2.4 Single fiber tensile testing

All group of fibers were fixed on the mounting cards with universal glue. Based on the ASTM standard (C1557-14), the prepared specimens were subject to tensile test at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min and with 10 mm gauge length. About 30 specimens were tested for each group.

2.5 Single fiber pull-out testing

The specimen preparation for single fiber pull-out test was similar to the method as described in our previous work [15], in short, the single fiber was stucked into a silicon rubber box by a needle, with the embedded length ranging from 200 to 600 μ m. Epoxy mixed with curing agent and accelerator was then poured into the box and cured at room temperature for 24 h. The specimens were post-cured at 60 °C for 2 h after they were carefully removed from the rubber box. At last, the prepared specimens were conducted to pull-out test at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min and with the gauge length of 10 mm. About 20 specimens were tested for each group.

2.6 Morphology characterization

The morphology of CNCs was observed by using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, PHILIPS XL30 FEG) and a transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Hitachi H-600). The surface morphology of un- and treated sisal fibers was also observed by using a SEM. The fractured surface of the pulled-out fibers was then investigated with an optical microscope.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Size distribution and morphologies of CNCs

Figure 2 shows SEM and TEM images of the manufactured CNCs which displayed a rod-like structure, similar to that observed in previous studies[16]. It can be seen that the MCC (20~80 μ m) was separated into nano-sized cellulose after sulphuric acid hydrolysis. MCC particles contain a lot of amorphous regions of cellulose, which are more prone to be hydrolyzed. Therefore, the obtained CNCs have nearly perfect crystalline structure, which render good mechanical properties for CNC particles. Meanwhile, the CNCs have a homogeneous size distribution by observing the micrographs of them. The dimensions of CNCs were measured by utilizing Image-Pro Plus 6.0, which exhibit

dimensions ranging from 20 to 30 nm in width and between 300 and 500 nm in length (Figure 3).

Figure 2: (a) SEM micrograph and (b) TEM micrograph of CNCs by acid hydrolysis of MCC.

Figure 3: Length distribution histogram of CNC particles.

3.2 Mechanical properties of the modified sisal fibers

Figure 4 shows the SEM images of the untreated and different treated sisal fibers. In Fig. 4(b), it was observed that 5 wt.% alkali-treated sisal fibers with clean and rough surfaces, which clearly presents a more suitable substrate for the CNCs adhesion than the untreated fibers (Fig. 4(a) and 4(d)). Compared to the untreated sisal fiber (Fig. 4(a) and 4(d)), Figure 4 (c) and 4(e) clearly show the presence of a mass of CNCs around the fibers. Meanwhile, CNCs were uniformly dispersed and randomly oriented on the surface of fibers.

Figure 4: SEM micrographs of sisal fiber surfaces: (a) untreated, (b) alkali-treated, (c) alkali-CNCs modified; (d) untreated (e) alkali-CNCs modified at high magnification.

The diameters and tensile properties of untreated and different treated sisal fibers are summarized in Table 1. With 5 wt% alkali treatment, the tensile strength and Young's modulus of the sisal fibers were increased by 31% and 38%, which was mostly due to the decreased in diameter of the fibers. During the alkali treatment process, the cell walls of fibers swelled and then shrank, leading to the decrease of the lumen size [7]. It was highly in agreement with the variation of diameter of alkali-treated fibers. Comparing to untreated sisal fibers, CNCs modified group has similar tensile properties, whereas, the Young's modulus of alkali-CNCs modified fibers reached 22 GPa increased by 62%. This suggests that it has a synergistic effect of strengthening the sisal fibers with alkali treatment and CNCs modification. As shown in Figure 5, the alkali treatment was carried out to partially remove of the lignin, hemicelluloses and other residues from the surface of the fibers [5, 8], roughening their surface (Figure 2 (b)). The EPD procedure made sisal fibers coated with a dense layer of CNCs. The CNCs particles could easily fill the gaps between the microfibrils etched or deepen by alkali treatment, and also carry some load or transfer it under the condition of loading through lots of hydrogen bonds. Compared to covalent bonding, the hydrogen bond energy is very small, which make the CNCs carry not much load before bonding rupture. It can be used to explain the tensile strength of CNCs modified fibers had no significant change. While coating of CNCs make the stress of microfibrils uniform during loading, combined with the high modulus of CNCs, resulting in a higher resistance to deformation for the fibers. Therefore the tensile modulus of alkali-treated fibers obtained a further increase after the CNCs modification.

Treatment	Diameter (μm)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)
Untreated	167.9	529.9 (102)	13.6 (2.9)
CNCs modified	175.3	511.5 (97)	14.4 (3.3)
Alkali-treated	142.6	692.8 (92)	18.8 (3.0)
Alkali-CNCs modified	146.8	614.9 (73)	22.0 (3.1)

Table 1: Mechanical properties of sisal fibers modified by different treatments.

Figure 5: The schematic of synergistic effect mechanism of alkali treatment and CNCs modification.

3.3 Interfacial properties of sisal/epoxy composites with alkali and CNCs treatments

The load-displacement curves obtained for the untreated and treated sisal fibers with the epoxy matrix during single fiber pull-out tests are given in Figure 6. Two different types of load-displacement curves have been observed. The untreated and alkali-treated sisal fibers are typical of unstable pull-out. While, the pull-outs of CNC-modified fibers turn into a relatively more stable process, which attributes to a mainly mechanically bonded interface as described by Kim et al. [17]. It illustrates that CNCs modification rendered extremely rough surface for both untreated and alkali-treated sisal fibers (Figure 4 (c) and 4 (e)), which could form lots of mechanical interlocking in the interface between fibers and matrix. With linearly fitting the plots of pull-out load-displacement curves (Figure 7), IFSS was obtained as the values of slopes, i.e., $\tau = P/(2\pi rl)$. Here P is the maximum pull-out load, r is the fiber radius, l is the embedded fiber length and embedded area equals to $2\pi rl$. It can be seen that the IFSS of alkali-treated group was shown considerably higher than that of the untreated group, increased by 35%. This could be on account of reduced poisson contraction and the removal of surface impurities on sisal fibers with alkali treatment, which is advantageous to fiber-matrix adhesion, as it facilitates both mechanical interlocking and the bonding reaction [8]. Whereas, the IFSS of the groups modified with CNCs shown no difference to that of untreated and alkali-treated group, although the fiber surface of CNCs modified groups was much rougher. According to the fracture theory of fiber-reinforced materials [18], IFSS is mainly influenced by interfacial adhesion and surface roughness. It is well-known that highly hydrophilic CNCs are poorly compatible with the hydrophobic epoxy, which obviously weakens the interfacial adhesion; while the roughly hierarchal structures modified with CNCs greatly promote mechanical interlocking in the interface. The two interfacial influencing mechanisms finally result in similar IFSS of sisal fibers with and without CNCs modification, meanwhile, remarkably improve the post-debond frictional pull-out force, which leads to no significant load drop after complete debonding. Owing to the high frictional force, it results in a significant increase in the energy absorbing capacity of the composites so as to improve the corresponding impact properties.

Figure 6: Load-displacement curves of pull-out tests for sisal/epoxy composites with different surface modifications.

Figure 7: Interfacial shear strength of sisal/epoxy composites with different surface modifications. Gradients, i.e., IFSS are calculated by linear fit of plots, with R2 equaling to 0.99, 0.97, 0.98 and 0.98.

In order to further elucidate and evaluate the interfacial characteristics, a theoretical model was adopted to calculate the interfacial parameters. Generally, there are two approaches to solve this problem: one is based on a maximum shear stress criterion; the other is based on fracture mechanics treating debonding. Among the two theories, Gao, Mai and Cotterell [18] proposed their own model based on the relationship between the debond and post-debond frictional pull-out stresses versus the embedded fiber length. It has been demonstrated that the model is able to determine the inherent interfacial properties, which is including interfacial fracture toughness, G_{ic} , coefficient of friction, μ , and the residual fiber clamping stress, q_0 .

In Gao-Mai-Cotterell's model, the initial frictional pull-out stress is expressed as

$$\sigma_{fr} = \bar{\sigma}[1 - \exp(-\lambda L)] \quad (1)$$

in which

$$\bar{\sigma} = -(q_0/k)[1+(\gamma/\alpha)(v_m/v_f)] \quad (2)$$

$$\lambda = 2\mu k/r_f \quad (3)$$

where

$$\alpha = E_m/E_f \quad (4)$$

$$\gamma = c_f/c_m \quad (5)$$

$$k = (\alpha v_f + \gamma v_m)/[\alpha(1-v_f)+1+v_m+2\gamma] \quad (6)$$

Where c_f , c_m are the volume fractions of the fiber and matrix. When $c_f \ll c_m$, γ can be ignored. E_f , E_m and v_f , v_m are the Young's moduli and Poisson's ratios for the fiber and matrix, respectively.

Based on Eqs. (1)-(3) and σ_{fr} versus L/r_f curves, q_0 and μ can be obtained by a graphical method (Figure 8). The parameters used to calculate these interfacial parameters are listed in Table 2 and the results are shown in Table 3.

Sisal fiber/Epoxy	E_f (GPa)	E_m (GPa)	v_f	v_m	k
Untreated	13				0.014
CNCs Modified	14	3.5	0.24	0.39	0.013
Alkali-treated	18				0.010
Alkali-CNCs Modified	22				0.008

Table 2: Materials parameters used in the calculations.

Figure 8: Theoretical predictions of interfacial parameters based on experimental results.

Sisal fiber/epoxy	τ (MPa)	q_0 (MPa)	μ
Untreated	31.4	3.3	4.1
CNCs Modified	30.4	3.3	9.7
Alkali-treated	42.3	3.3	5.2
Alkali-CNCs Modified	38.3	3.3	10.4

Table 3: Interfacial properties of different treated sisal/epoxy composites.

It can be seen that the calculated frictional coefficients of CNCs-Modified groups are two times higher than that of groups without CNCs modification. However, there are no obviously effect of improving frictional coefficients for alkali treatment. This result could be further verified by the optical microscope images of fractured surfaces of pulled-out fibers (Figure 9). It is observed that lots of resin residues (black arrow) are adhered to the surface of fibers modified with CNCs, whereas, untreated and alkali-treated groups are relatively clean. It demonstrate that the surface of CNCs modified sisal fibers becomes much rougher than that of fibers without CNCs modification.

Figure 9: Optical microscope images of fractured surfaces of the pulled-out fibers with various treatment: (a) untreated, (b) CNC modified, (c) alkali-treated and (d) alkali-CNCs modified.

4 CONCLUSIONS

EPD of CNCs has been successfully employed to modify sisal fibers, with SEM characterization showing consistent outcomes. With 5 wt% alkali treatment, the tensile strength and Young's modulus of the sisal fibers were increased by 31% and 38%; with both alkali and CNCs modification, the Young's modulus of fibers further reached up to 22 GPa increased by 62%, which shows there is a synergistic effect of strengthening the sisal fibers with alkali treatment and CNCs modification.

In aspect of interfacial properties, it can be concluded that alkali treatment of fibers improved IFSS by 35% because of obtaining better interfacial adhesion; hydrophilic CNCs weaken the interface compatibility between fibers and epoxy, which slightly decreased their IFSS, however, remarkably improved the post-debond frictional pull-out force due to the large surface roughness of fibers. The frictional coefficients of fibers with different treatment were calculated by Gao-Mai-Cotterel's theoretical model, which shows frictional coefficients of CNCs-Modified fibers are more than two times than that of fibers without CNCs modification. The large frictional coefficient plays an important role in improving the damping and impact properties of fiber reinforced composites. Therefore, in the future we will investigate the effect of CNCs modification on the damping and impact properties of natural fiber reinforced composites.

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